

Dynamic homogenization of random heterogeneous beams

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Abstract

The paper deals with the differences between apparent and effective solution in case of dynamic homogenization of continuous media with random micro-structure. In particular, these differences, called “residuals”, are considered for the dynamic linear problem of the Euler-Bernoulli’s beam with random Young’s modulus.

The differential operator with random coefficient, that describes the eigenvalues problem, is taken into account. The convergence to the effective solution is analysed by introducing two measures: the normalized error between apparent and effective Young’s modulus and the normalized error between the modes shapes.

The obtained results permit to highlight the dependence of the residuals from the micro-structure dimensionless length and the effect of the modes order; these aspects should be considered in homogenization of random heterogeneous composites. Moreover, it is underlined that, to obtain an adequate evaluation of the response in dynamic problem, the RVE’s dimension estimation is depending on the frequency characteristics of the force.

Keywords: Dynamic Homogenization, Random Heterogeneous Euler-Bernoulli’s Beam, Residuals

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1. Introduction

When dealing with a heterogeneous material with periodic micro-structure it is sufficient to analyse the Periodic Unit Cell (PUC) to evaluate the characteristics of the equivalent homogeneous material. In case of random micro-structures it is necessary to individuate the Representative Volume Element (RVE) (Sab, 1992).

Several definitions of RVE have been proposed by researchers for different purposes. Following Hill (1963), RVE is a sample that is representative of the whole mixture in average and contains a sufficient number of inclusions so that its apparent overall moduli are macroscopically uniform. In fact, the RVE is the smallest material volume, sufficiently larger than micro-structure size, for which the spatially overall moduli description is accurate to represent the mean response (Drugan and Willis, 1996).

Introducing the micro-meso, and macroscales principle (Hashin, 1983), the RVE should contain a very large (mathematically infinite) set of microscale elements (e.g. grains) possessing statically homogeneous and ergodic proprieties (Hostogia-Starzewki, 2008). Considering a mesoscale sample with finite dimensions (this is sometimes indicated as Statistical Volume Element - SVE) its propriety are described by the adjective apparent (Huet, 1990) as opposed to effective ones which denote the RVE, so that the problem is to find the scatter and the convergence rate of SVE to RVE.

The RVE size estimation has been taken into account in several papers (Gitman et al., 2006) (Gitman et al., 2007) (Kanit et al., 2003) also considering the effects on material properties evaluation (He, 2001); this aspect plays an important role in case, for example, of quasi-periodic material homogenization as masonry with random texture (Cluni and Gusella, 2004) (Gusella and Cluni, 2006). Moreover it well known that the analysis of non-local interactions between heterogeneities is necessary when the spatial variation of the considered physical quantities, relative to the micro-structure, cannot be ignored (Luciano and Willis, 2005).

Facing this theme from a mathematical point of view, the homogenization can be regarded as the study of the asymptotic behaviour and convergence of differential operators with variable coefficients. Starting from the initial contributions (Stampacchia, 1965), the literature devoted to homogenization with oscillatory periodic coefficients is very wide (Bensoussan et al., 1978)

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(Bakhvalov and Panasenko, 1989).

Regarding the operators with random coefficients, after the first important solutions obtained by Kozlov (1980) and Papanicolau and Varadhan (1979) several contributions have been reported in literature (Jikov et al., 1994).

Nevertheless the measure of the difference between the heterogeneous solution (apparent solution) and the homogenized solution (effective solution), that is indicated as *residual* or *corrector*, has had a more limited attention.

At first, the paper of Pozhidaev and Yurinskii (1990) gave some successful attempts in case of second-order elliptic random operators.

The estimation of the discrepancy between solutions has been considered by Bourgeat and Piatnitski for a one-dimensional second-order elliptic operators with random coefficients satisfying strong (Bourgeat and Piatnitski, 1999) and different mixing condition (Bourgeat and Piatnitski, 2004). This problem has been examined in depth for long-range correlations by Bal et al. (2008).

In order to analyse the residuals in case of bi-phase medium with different quasi periodic texture, the problem of the convergence rate has been addressed considering the beam model with random Young's modulus (Cluni and Gusella, 2014). Moreover, the analysis has recently been extended to a two-dimensional problem (Cluni and Gusella, 2017).

As far as the authors' knowledge is concerned, no results about homogenization residuals for structural dynamic problems have been reported in literature. In the present paper, this aspect is dealt with by considering the linear elastic dynamic equation of the Euler-Bernoulli's Beam with random Young's modulus.

2. Statement of the problem

Observing that "random differential operators", namely differential operators with random coefficients, will be later considered, the following assumptions and definitions have to be introduced.

Let $(\Omega, \mathfrak{S}, P)$ be a standard probability space, i.e. a set Ω equipped with a σ -algebra \mathfrak{S} of measurable subsets and a countably additive non-negative measure P normalized by $P(\Omega) = 1$. We always assume the measure P to be complete (Pankov, 1997).

Let assume that a d -dimensional dynamical system T_x , $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is given on Ω (Bourgeat and Piatnitski, 2004), i.e. a family of invertible measurable

maps $T_x : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$, such that

- $T_{x+y} = T_x T_y$, $T_0 = Id$,
- $P \{(T_x)^{-1}(A)\} = P \{(A)\}$ for any $A \in \mathfrak{S}$ and any $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, that is T_x preserve the measure P ,
- T_x is a measurable mapping from $\mathbb{R}^d \times \Omega$ to Ω where $\mathbb{R}^d \times \Omega$ is equipped with the product σ -algebra $\mathbb{B} \times \mathfrak{S}$ and \mathbb{B} is the Borel σ -algebra \mathbb{R}^d .

For an arbitrary random variable $f = f(\omega)$ we define $f(\omega, z) = f(T_z \omega)$ that is a statistically homogeneous random field; moreover we assume that T_z is an ergodic dynamical system (Bourgeat and Piatnitski, 2004).

Let us consider the flexural vibration of the Euler-Bernoulli's beam, Fig. 1(A). The motion is described by the partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(E(\omega, y) J \frac{\partial^2 v^\varepsilon(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right) + \mu \frac{\partial^2 v^\varepsilon(x, t)}{\partial t^2} = f(x, t) \quad (1)$$

where $v^\varepsilon(x, t)$ is the stochastic field of the transverse displacement, $0 \leq x \leq L$, ε is the length parameter that characterizes the micro-structure, $y = \varepsilon^{-1}x$ and $E(\omega, y) = E(T_y \omega) = E(T_{x/\varepsilon} \omega)$ Young's modulus is a ergodic homogeneous random field with $0 < c_1 < E(\omega, y) < c_2 < \infty$.

In the previous equation, the ρ linear mass density and the J transversal section inertia moment assume deterministic values constant along x ; moreover $f(x, t)$ is the external transverse force that is assumed deterministic. To complete the formulation of the dynamic boundary-value problem, it is necessary to specify the boundary condition and the initial conditions.

[Figure 1 about here.]

The previous equation can be resolved by the superposition of the normal modes.

Regarding the eigenvalue problem, we consider the free vibrations characterized by $f(x, t) = 0$ and the solution becomes separable in space and time

$$v^\varepsilon(x, t) = u^\varepsilon(x) g^\varepsilon(t) \quad (2)$$

whence

$$g^\varepsilon(t) \frac{d}{dx^2} \left(E(\omega, y) \frac{J}{\rho} \frac{d^2 u^\varepsilon(x)}{dx^2} \right) + u^\varepsilon(x) \frac{d^2 g^\varepsilon(t)}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

and

$$-\frac{\frac{d^2 g^\varepsilon(t)}{dt^2}}{g^\varepsilon(t)} = \frac{\frac{d}{dx^2} \left(E(\omega, y) \frac{J}{\rho} \frac{d^2 u^\varepsilon(x)}{dx^2} \right)}{u^\varepsilon(x)} = \text{const} = (\lambda^\varepsilon)^2 \quad (4)$$

We obtain the following equations:

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left(E(\omega, y) \frac{J}{\rho} \frac{d^2 u^\varepsilon(x)}{dx^2} \right) - (\lambda^\varepsilon)^2 u^\varepsilon(x) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2} g^\varepsilon(t) + (\lambda^\varepsilon)^2 g^\varepsilon(t) = 0 \quad (6)$$

which correspond to a eigenproblem of a beam with random Young's modulus. Given the boundary conditions, for each choice of $E(\omega, y)$ we obtain the eigenvalues $(\lambda^\varepsilon)_k^2$ (and relative own frequencies $(\lambda^\varepsilon)_k$) and the eigenvectors (normal modes) $u_k^\varepsilon(x)$ with $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

The main results on the asymptotic behaviour of random differential operators were first obtained by Kozlov (1980) and Papanicolau and Varadhan (1979), based on a formal analogy between periodic media and statistically homogeneous ergodic media. Further developments are reported in Jikov et al. (1994) and in the quoted literature there. Given these results, when $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, $u^\varepsilon(x)$, in Eq. 5, converges for a.e. ω to $u^o(x)$ which is the deterministic solution of the homogenised problem

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left(\bar{E} \frac{J}{\mu} \frac{d^2 u^o(x)}{dx^2} \right) - (\lambda^o)^2 u^o(x) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d^4 u^o(x)}{dx^4} - \frac{(\lambda^o)^2 \mu}{\bar{E} J} u^o(x) = 0 \quad (8)$$

where, indicating with μ the average operator,

$$\bar{E} = (\mu \{1/E(\omega, 0)\})^{-1} \quad (9)$$

Let $(\lambda_k^o)^2$ and $u_k^o(x)$ be the eigenvalues (squares of natural frequencies) and eigenfunctions (modes) the classical deterministic Euler-Bernoulli's beam problem, with \bar{E} constant Young's modulus. So that, as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ we have $(\lambda_k^\varepsilon)^2 \rightarrow (\lambda_k^o)^2$ and $u_k^\varepsilon(x) \rightarrow u_k^o(x)$ with $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$; our aim is to check the convergence and estimate its rate.

3. Discrete approach

In order to check the convergence and to estimate the residuals, the continuous eigenproblem is addressed using a discrete approach. The problem can be related to the analysis of natural frequencies and mode shapes of the Euler-Bernoulli's beam with step changes in cross-section (Jang and Bert, 1989a) (Jang and Bert, 1989b).

Let us consider the beam composed by N collinear elements with length Δl_j $j = 1, \dots, N$ with $\Delta l_j = \Delta l = L/N$, Fig. 1(B).

Moreover we assume that these elements have same J inertial moment and ρ density but E_j different Young's modulus. Without loss of generality, the beam clamped at the ends is considered.

The eigenproblem can be described by a N -differential equations system

$$\frac{d^4 u_j(x_j)}{dx_j^4} - \frac{\lambda^2 \rho}{E_j J} u_j(x_j) = 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, N \quad (10)$$

where $x_j \in [0, \Delta l]$.

Moreover we have the following the $4N$ boundary conditions

$$u_1(0) = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\left. \frac{d^2 u_1}{dx_1^2} \right|_{x_1=0} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$u_l(\Delta l) = u_{l+1}(0) \quad (13)$$

$$\left. \frac{du_l}{dx_l} \right|_{x_l=\Delta l} = \left. \frac{du_{l+1}}{dx_{l+1}} \right|_{x_{l+1}=0} \quad (14)$$

$$E_j \left. \frac{du_l^2}{dx_l^2} \right|_{x_l=\Delta l} = E_{l+1} \left. \frac{du_{l+1}^2}{dx_{l+1}^2} \right|_{x_{l+1}=0} \quad (15)$$

$$E_l \left. \frac{du_l^3}{dx_l^3} \right|_{x_l=\Delta l} = E_{l+1} \left. \frac{du_{l+1}^3}{dx_{l+1}^3} \right|_{x_{l+1}=0} \quad (16)$$

$$u_N(\Delta l) = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\left. \frac{d^2 u_N}{dx_N^2} \right|_{x_N = \Delta l} = 0 \quad (18)$$

where $l = 1, \dots, N - 1$.

The $\lambda_{N,k}$ natural frequencies and the $u_{N,k}$ relative modal shapes, with $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, correspond to not banal solutions of the previous equations system. They have to depend on the number on collinear elements N and Young's modulus of each element:

$$\lambda_{N,k} = \lambda_{N,k}(E_1, \dots, E_N) \quad (19)$$

$$u_{N,k} = u_{N,k}(E_1, \dots, E_N) \quad (20)$$

Also for a limited value of N , the analytical solution appears very burdensome, so a numerical procedure is preferred (Naguleswaran, 2002).

4. Numerical approach

The beam is divided in finite elements, numbered $j_e = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N_e$, with equal length $l_e = L/N_e$, Fig. 1(C). The stiffness and mass matrices are evaluated by well known expressions proposed in literature (Bathe, 1996).

In the present analysis the number of finite elements is $N_e = 240$ and it can be checked that this assumption assures, for the first own frequencies and modal shapes, a very negligible disagreement among our numerical results and ones reported in literature in case of a limited number of step change in cross-section.

In order to study the beam with micro-structure, the following procedure is used.

Adjacent finite elements are considered in groups; each group has $N_g = N_e/N$ elements. Considering the first group, all elements have the same Young's modulus E_1 ; the second group E_2 , and so on. So that the beam is supposed composed by $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ micro-elements, where $N = N_e/N_g$, with constant modulus E_j and length $l_g = N_g l_e = N_g L/N_e$.

With reference previous chapter, adopting $l_g = \Delta L$ the heterogeneity dimensionless length is $\varepsilon = l_g/L = N_g/N_e = 1/N$.

It should be noted that the number of finite elements, in every analysis, is always N_e to reduce the effect of the numerical errors.

5. Random model for Young's modulus

Let us assume an uniform distribution for $E(\omega)$ Young's modulus with probability density function

$$p_E(E) = \begin{cases} 1/(E_2 - E_1) & E_1 < E < E_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

with mean $\mu_E = \mu(E) = (E_2 - E_1)/2$.

Let be $C = 1/E$ the inverse of the Young's modulus.

Noting $y = C = 1/E = 1/x$ with $1/E_2 < C < 1/E_1$, we have $dy/dx = -1/x^2 = -y^2$ and $dx/dy = -1/y^2$; the probability density function of y is $p_y(y) = p_x(x) |dx/dy|$.

The mean value of the C is

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_C &= \int_{1/E_2}^{1/E_1} y p_y dy = \frac{1}{E_2 - E_1} \int_{1/E_2}^{1/E_1} y \left| -\frac{1}{y^2} \right| dy = \\ &= \frac{1}{E_2 - E_1} \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{E_1} \right) - \ln \left(\frac{1}{E_2} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{E_2 - E_1} \ln \left(\frac{E_2}{E_1} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

With reference to Eq. 9

$$\bar{E} = \frac{1}{\mu_C} = \frac{E_2 - E_1}{\ln(E_2/E_1)} \quad (23)$$

In the numerical analysis the following values have been considered $E_1 = \mu_E/2$ and $E_2 = 3\mu_E/2$, so that $\bar{E} = \mu_E/\ln(3)$.

6. Convergence and residuals

Let us consider the homogenized beam with the \bar{E} "effective Young's modulus" (Eq. 23); it is well known that angular frequencies and modes (square root of eigenvalues and the eigenfunctions) are:

$$\lambda_k = k^2 \frac{\pi^2}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{E}J}{\rho}} \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (24)$$

$$u_k = u_k(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin \left(\frac{k\pi x}{L} \right) \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (25)$$

The previous correspond to the effective homogenized solution.

Let us now consider the beam composed by N micro-elements with ΔL length, so that $\varepsilon = \Delta L/L$. The Young's moduli vector (E_1, \dots, E_N) is obtained by independent extractions from previously described uniform distribution, Eq. 21.

The natural frequencies $\lambda_{N,k} = \lambda_{\varepsilon,k} \in \Re$ and modes $\mathbf{u}_{N,k} = \mathbf{u}_{\varepsilon,k} \in \Re^{N_e+1}$ can be numerically obtained by FE model; it should be noted that numerical modes are evaluated on the joints of the finite element model with abscissa $x_v = (v-1)l_e$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\varepsilon,k} = [(u_{\varepsilon,k})_v] \quad v = 1, \dots, N_e + 1 \quad (26)$$

For every k angular frequency, the Young's modulus of the equivalent homogeneous beam is evaluated by

$$E_{N,k} = E_{\varepsilon,k} = \lambda_{Nk}^2 \left(\frac{L}{k\pi} \right)^4 \frac{\rho}{J} \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (27)$$

This can be regarded as an "apparent Young's moduls", so that the residual can be highlighted by the following measure (or normalized error)

$$\Delta E_{\varepsilon,k} = \frac{E_{\varepsilon,k} - \bar{E}}{\bar{E}} \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (28)$$

Moreover, for every k angular frequency, an other residual correspond to the difference between the u_k effective and $u_{\varepsilon,k}$ apparent modes; the following $\Delta u_{\varepsilon,k} \in \Re$ measure (or normalized errors) can be introduced:

$$\Delta u_{\varepsilon,k} = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L |u_{\varepsilon,k} - u_k| dx \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (29)$$

By comparison (25) and (26) we obtained

$$\Delta u_{\varepsilon,k} = \frac{1}{N_e} \sum_{v=1}^{N_e+1} |(u_{\varepsilon,k})_v - u_k(x_v)| \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (30)$$

Given ε and considering the randomness of the Young's moduli vector, the following random variables are introduced

$$\tilde{\Delta} E_{\varepsilon,k} \quad \tilde{\Delta} u_{\varepsilon,k} \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (31)$$

The statistical analysis of the variables permits to estimate the homogenization residuals behaviour; in the present study, samples with $M = 5,000$ cases (i.e. M simulations of the vector (E_1, \dots, E_N)), are considered for each value of ε .

Let be $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ and $s(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ the mean and the standard deviation of the $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$ random variable. The relationship $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ versus ε is shown in Fig. 2 for different values of the k mode order; the behaviour of $s(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ is shown in Fig. 3.

[Figure 2 about here.]

[Figure 3 about here.]

It should be noted that $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$, that can be assumed as a representative value for Young's modulus residuals, converges to the \bar{E} effective modulus as ε decreases. Nevertheless the rate is varying with the mode order; in particular, fixed a value for ε , the approximation is worse increasing the k mode order.

This behaviour is also highlighted by analysing the histogram of the random variable $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$. As example, the histograms, for different ε values, are reported in Fig. 4 and 5, for $k = 1$ and $k = 5$ mode order respectively; the Gaussian probability density functions, with first and second moments equal to the histograms ones, are reported in the same figures, it should be noted that the fitting is accurate.

[Figure 4 about here.]

[Figure 5 about here.]

In order to understand the behaviour of the residuals, it should be noted that to fix a ε value is equivalent to adopt a beam with N collinear elements; so that the obtained results correspond to the statistical sample of the frequencies, given by Eq. 19, and equivalent Young's modulus, given by Eq. 27.

In this case the homogenization result still holds with the only difference that the apparent coefficient is not deterministic but a measurable random variable respect to the σ -algebra of sets.

As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ the random Young's modulus becomes an ergodic field and the apparent moduli converge to the deterministic effective value; this is shown

by $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}) \rightarrow \bar{E}$, (Fig.2); moreover, in this case $s(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}) \rightarrow 0$ (Fig 3) and the probability density function degenerates into a Dirac function (Fig.4 and Fig. 5).

This is valid for every mode order but the convergence rate is different; this behaviour can be explained because of the interaction between the heterogeneity length and the characteristic spatial length of the mode shape which is the distance between successive nodes. The obtained results underline that the micro-structure length should not be compared with the L beam length but with the L/k distance between two successive nodes when the k order mode is considered. Therefore, an adequate homogenization approach requires $k\varepsilon \ll L$; it is worth noting that the condition $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ is sufficient to assure that previous interaction is overcome.

Previous observations can be confirmed by the statistical analysis of the $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ random variable that gives a measure of the difference between apparent and effective mode shape.

The behaviour of the $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k})$ mean and $s(\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k})$ standard deviation are reported in Fig. 6 and 7, respectively.

The histograms of $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 for $k = 1$ and $k = 5$ mode order, respectively; the Log-normal probability density functions, with first and second moments equal to the histograms ones, are reported in the same figures, it should be noted that the fitting is sufficiently accurate.

[Figure 6 about here.]

[Figure 7 about here.]

[Figure 8 about here.]

[Figure 9 about here.]

It is well known that dynamic response is strongly affected by the resonance phenomenon among structure natural frequencies and force ones; so that, the obtained results highlight that an accurate choice of the RVE's dimension, in the homogenized approach, have to depend to the frequency characteristics of the force, especially with coloured spectrum.

7. Conclusions

This paper considers the homogenization of dynamic problem of random heterogeneous media with special attention to the residuals namely the differences between apparent solutions and effective solution. This topic has been considered with regards to the eigenanalysis of the Euler-Bernouilli's beam with random Young's modulus.

Referring to the main results relative to the homogenization of differential operators with random coefficient, two residuals have been proposed: the normalized error between apparent and effective modulus and the normalised error between apparent and effective modal shape. The analysis is performed into discrete field, by considering the beam composed by collinear elements, using the finite element approach.

The results, obtained in this first step of the ongoing research, permit to highlight the convergence of the residuals versus the micro-structure dimensionless length and the effect of the mode order; these aspects should be considered in homogenization of random heterogeneous composites.

Furthermore it is underlined, that in dynamic problem, the RVE dimensions can be strongly depended on the force frequency characteristic especially with coloured spectrum.

Further studies are necessary to consider the effect of different correlation laws of the Young's modulus and the analysis have to be extended to two-dimensional dynamic problems.

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List of Figures

1	Mechanical model: (A) Euler-Bernoulli's continuous beam; (B) discrete approach: beam with collinear elements; (C) finite element model	17
2	$\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective Young's modulus - behaviour of $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ mean versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: o $\leftrightarrow k = 1$; x $\leftrightarrow k = 2$; + $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $\star \leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$	18
3	$\tilde{\Delta}sE_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective Young's modulus - behaviour of $s(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ standard deviation versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: o $\leftrightarrow k = 1$; x $\leftrightarrow k = 2$; + $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $\star \leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$	19
4	Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 1$ mode order, and fitting Gaussian probability density functions	20
5	Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 5$ mode order, and fitting Gaussian probability density functions	21
6	$\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective modal shape - behaviour of $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k})$ mean versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: o $\leftrightarrow k = 1$; x $\leftrightarrow k = 2$; + $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $\star \leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$	22
7	$\tilde{\Delta}s u_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective modal shape - behaviour of $s(\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k})$ standard deviation versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: o $\leftrightarrow k = 1$; x $\leftrightarrow k = 2$; + $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $\star \leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$	23
8	Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 1$ mode order, and fitting Log-normal probability density functions	24
9	Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 5$ mode order, and fitting Log-normal probability density functions	25

Figure 1: Mechanical model: (A) Euler-Bernoulli's continuous beam; (B) discrete approach: beam with collinear elements; (C) finite element model

Figure 2: $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective Young's modulus - behaviour of $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ mean versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: $o \leftrightarrow k = 1$; $x \leftrightarrow k = 2$; $+$ $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $*$ $\leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$

Figure 3: $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective Young's modulus - behaviour of $s(\tilde{\Delta}E_{\varepsilon,k})$ standard deviation versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: o $\leftrightarrow k = 1$; x $\leftrightarrow k = 2$; + $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; * $\leftrightarrow k = 4$; □ $\leftrightarrow k = 5$; ◇ $\leftrightarrow k = 6$; ▽ $\leftrightarrow k = 7$; △ $\leftrightarrow k = 8$

Figure 4: Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\epsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 1$ mode order, and fitting Gaussian probability density functions

Figure 5: Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}E_{\epsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 5$ mode order, and fitting Gaussian probability density functions

Figure 6: $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective modal shape - behaviour of $\mu(\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k})$ mean versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: $\circ \leftrightarrow k = 1$; $\times \leftrightarrow k = 2$; $+$ $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $*$ $\leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$

Figure 7: $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k}$ residuals respect to the effective modal shape - behaviour of $s(\tilde{\Delta}u_{\varepsilon,k})$ standard deviation versus ε micro-structure dimensionless length; k mode number: $\circ \leftrightarrow k = 1$; $\times \leftrightarrow k = 2$; $+$ $\leftrightarrow k = 3$; $\star \leftrightarrow k = 4$; $\square \leftrightarrow k = 5$; $\diamond \leftrightarrow k = 6$; $\nabla \leftrightarrow k = 7$; $\triangle \leftrightarrow k = 8$

Figure 8: Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\epsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 1$ mode order, and fitting Log-normal probability density functions

Figure 9: Histograms of the $\tilde{\Delta}u_{\epsilon,k}$ residuals, for $k = 5$ mode order, and fitting Log-normal probability density functions